

Crop-weed competition in direct seeded flooded and rainfed banded rice

A. M. Ali and S. Sankaran, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore 641003, India

Effect of weed treatments on grain yield of direct seeded rice, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Monsoons		Summer	
	Flooded	Rainfed	Flooded	Rainfed
Unweeded control	1.6	0.5	2.1	0.0
Weed free up to				
10 d	1.7	1.0	2.1	0.2
20 d	2.4	1.4	3.5	0.4
30 d	3.5	2.7	4.2	0.6
40 d	4.0	3.3	4.3	0.9
50 d	4.4	3.5	4.3	1.5
60 d	4.2	3.6	4.5	1.7
70 d	4.3	3.7	4.5	1.9
80 d	4.2	4.0	4.4	2.2
90 d	4.2	4.1	4.2	2.2
CD for weed-free control at rice systems			424	
CD for rice system at weed-free control			503	

Field experiments with direct-seeded Bhavani at TNAU in monsoon and summer seasons showed that *Echinochloa crus-galli* was the predominant grass weed in flooded rice and *Echinochloa colona* in rainfed rice. The weeds competed with rice at all stages. *Cyperus difformis* was the predominant sedge, and caused severe competition with the early flooded crop. *Cyperus iria* was the dominant weed in rainfed rice. *Eclipta alba* was a dominant dicot weed under both conditions. In flooded rice, *Ammannia baccifera* and *Marsilea quadrifolia* were dominant.

Based on grain yield (see table), a weed-free period of 50 d in monsoon and 30 d in summer improved flooded rice

yield. To get high yields in rainfed rice, 60 d was needed in monsoon and 70 d in summer. □

Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Breeding, movement, and populations of mice in Thailand

P. Sudto, S. Bamrongsook, and P. Boonsong, Zoology Section, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, P. O. Box 9-34, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

Mark and release trapping was used to study the movement and population of

mice *Mus cervicolor* and *M. caroli* in a rice field in Chainat Province, about 180 km north of Bangkok, where rice was cultivated only in rainy season (Jun-Sep). Mice were trapped from 4 plots for 5 nights each month. Plots were about 500 m apart. From Jan to Jun, when no rice is grown, mouse traps were in a 7 × 7 grid placed at 10-m intervals, 49 traps to each plot. From Jul to Dec 1980 a trap-line along the dikes was used because fields were flooded.

Most mice caught (533 or 87.8%) were *M. cervicolor* (see table). Seventy-seven (12.2%) *M. caroli* were trapped. Maximum catches were in Mar, Apr, and May. The longest midpoint of movement (radius of greatest distance) was 29.4 m. Home range as based on 127, 35, and 19 recaptures in Mar, Apr, and May respectively, was 421.2 m². Breeding activity, determined by number of pregnant females trapped, occurred in late Jan and early Feb, Jul, Sep, and Oct. □

Variation of temperature, relative humidity, rainfall, habitat, breeding activity, number of mice trapped, midpoint of movement, and size of home range for *M. cervicolor* and *M. caroli*.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Max temp °C	35	36.4	38.6	38	34.1	33.6	33	33.2	22.9	32.2	30.1	32.6
Min temp °C	9.6	11.0	15.4	16	34.4	22.5	22	21.6	21.3	20.8	18.7	10.0
RH (%)	67	81	79	77	78	79	83	80	81	78	81	69
Rainfall (mm)	0	47.7	23.8	72.7	2.9	1.5	5.9	2.9	7.4	1.8	8.3	0
Habitat ^a	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	1
Breeding activity	0	70%	0	0	0	0	33.33%	0	100%	75	0	0
<i>M. cervicolor</i> trapped	0	4	294	152	73	5	16	11	3	5	0	0
<i>M. caroli</i> trapped	0	1	32	13	4	1	15	5	2	4	0	0
Midpoint of movement (m)	0	0	12.36	13.82	8.29	0	29.45	10	20	0	0	0
Home range (m ²)	0	0	347.07	421.25	263.16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

^a 1 = after harvest, 2 = burn straw, 3 = dried, 4 = plow, 5 = broadcasting, 6 = age of rice 1 mo, 7-9 = age of rice 2, 3, 4 mo, 10 = milk stage to harvesting.